

**D6.2 - INITIAL DISSEMINATION,
COMMUNICATION AND STAKEHOLDER
ENGAGEMENT REPORT**

Work package	WP6 Communication, dissemination, exploitation and sustainability
Task	T6.2 Stakeholder engagement T6.3 Collaboration with other projects and initiatives
Due date	30/04/2024
Submission date	30/04/2024
Deliverable lead	FVA
Version	V4.0
Authors	Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini, Gabor Mester
Reviewers	Louis Ferrini, Gülşah Yılan, Ilenia Manetti

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
1.0	22/03/2023	Initial structure of the deliverable	Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini, Louis Ferrini
2.0	08/04/2023	Advanced version of the deliverable and collection of partners' inputs	Gabor Mester, Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini, Louis Ferrini, All partners
3.0	12/04/2023	Quality check by the COO	Gülşah Yılan, Ilenia Manetti
4.0	23/04/2023	Final version of the deliverable ready to be submitted	Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini

Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process.

The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives.

This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union under project number 101081823. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright notice: © 2022 - 2025 SUSTRACK Project

Nature of the deliverable:		*R
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

SUSTRACK Consortium

#	Participant Organization Name	Short Name	Country
1	UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA	UNIT	IT
2	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
3	KNOWLEDGE SRL	KE	IT
4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
5	DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
7	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	ES
8	FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C	FVA	IT
9	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	IT
10	BUNDESANSTALT FÜR MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	DE
11	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIÓN DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	CIRCE	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D6.2 updates on the progress about dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement tools and activities implemented from the beginning of the project to M18 (April 2024), based on the strategies, methodologies, channels, materials and tools described in details in the deliverable D6.1 “Initial Dissemination and Communication plan”.

Several tools have been produced (and constantly updated when necessary) during the first 18 months of the project, such as website, flyers, roll-up, project video and presentation, as well as publications, factsheets, promotional banners, thematic cards, newsletter and press releases.

Many dissemination and communication activities were carried out, thanks to the commitment and collaboration of all partners throughout the first half of the project, including speeches at conferences, meetings, education and training events and participation into events and exhibitions specifically dedicated to large public and youngsters.

Finally, as stakeholder engagement stands as a key cornerstone of the SUSTRACK project and their involvement ensures that project outcomes are shared and validated among the target groups, SUSTRACK organized various stakeholder engagement activities, namely co-creation focus groups, interviews, surveys, meetings and conferences.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	13
2	Dissemination and Communication tools	14
2.1	Overview of Dissemination and Communication channels and tools.....	14
2.2	Brand identity kit.....	17
2.3	Website	17
2.3.1	“Advisory board” section	17
2.3.2	“Outcomes” section	17
2.3.3	News page	18
2.4	Flyers.....	19
2.5	Roll-ups	20
2.6	Posters	20
2.7	Project presentation.....	20
2.8	Publications	20
2.9	Case study factsheets.....	21
2.10	Conference outcome factsheets	22
2.11	Case studies videos.....	23
2.12	Infographic cards	23
2.13	Toolkits	23
2.14	Promotional video.....	24
2.15	Video teasers for social media campaigns	24
2.16	Promotional banners.....	25
2.17	Thematic cards	26
2.18	Email campaigns.....	28
2.19	Newsletters.....	29
2.20	Press releases	29
2.21	Social media profiles.....	30

2.22	Social media campaigns	31
2.22.1	“INSPIRE Conference” social media campaign	31
2.22.2	“Cluster of barriers” social media campaign	33
2.23	Other graphical materials	34
3	Dissemination and Communication activities.....	40
3.1	Dissemination activities	40
3.1.1	Conferences	41
3.1.2	Meetings.....	41
3.2	Dissemination activities in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded projects 43	
3.2.1	Education and Training events.....	46
3.3	Communication activities	47
3.3.1	Event and Exhibition	47
3.3.2	Promotion of SUSTRACK in external Newsletters	51
3.3.3	Promotion of SUSTRACK in partners’ and other Social Media	52
3.3.4	Promotion of SUSTRACK in partners’ website	53
3.4	Lessons learnt and recommendation for the second half of the project.....	54
4	Stakeholder engagement activities	55
4.1	Continuous identification and involvement of SUSTRACK project stakeholders	55
4.2	SUSTRACK advisory board	55
4.3	Overall details of SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement activities	55
4.3.1	Focus group workshop.....	63
4.3.2	Interviews.....	65
4.3.3	Survey	65
4.3.4	Online workshops/meetings with stakeholders.....	65
4.3.5	INSPIRE conference.....	65
4.4	Lessons learnt and recommendation for the second half of the project.....	72

5	Collaboration with other projects and initiatives	74
5.1	Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM (organised by SUSTRACK)	75
5.1.1	Online “Cooperation Launching Event” (9 March 2023)	76
5.1.2	First Thematic Discussion Meeting (20 April 2023)	77
5.2	Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” (organised by SUSTRACK)	78
5.2.1	1 st Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop (14 February 2023)	80
5.2.2	“Sister projects” section on SUSTRACK website	81
5.3	Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” in which SUSTRACK representatives participated	82
5.4	Clustering activities with other projects and initiatives in bioeconomy	84
5.4.1	Clustering activities with ECOSYSTEMEX initiative	84
5.5	Lessons learnt and next steps	88
6	Next steps and conclusion	90

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the "Advisory Board" section on SUSTRACK website	17
Figure 2 - Screenshot of the "Outcomes" section on SUSTRACK website	18
Figure 3 - Screenshots of the "News" section on SUSTRACK website.....	19
Figure 4 - SUSTRACK flyers distribution in Researchers Night 2023.....	20
Figure 5 -Two pages of the INSPIRE Conference factsheet.....	23
Figure 6 - Screenshot of the SUSTRACK promotional video	24
Figure 7 - Screenshot of the first SUSTRACK video teaser	25
Figure 8 - Promotional banners shared on SUSTRACK social media	26
Figure 9 - Thematic cards used for the "Cluster of barriers" social media campaign	28
Figure 10 -Screenshots of two pages of the newsletter	29
Figure 11 - Examples of social media posts	31
Figure 12 -Cards used for the "INSPIRE conference" social media campaign	33
Figure 13 - A couple of screenshots of the "Cluster of barriers" social media campaign	34
Figure 14 - Methodology of the SUSTRACK co-creation focus group workshop.....	35
Figure 15 - Screening criteria for the identification of policy goals and Biotransition, Biorevolution scenarios' icons.....	35
Figure 16 - Visualisation of the CBBE definition	36
Figure 17 - Timeline of task T1.2	36
Figure 18 - Identification and consolidation process of the barriers to a CBBE (T1.2).....	37
Figure 19 - Methodological steps of the interviews (T1.2)	37
Figure 20 - Primary and secondary objectives of interviews (T1.2)	38
Figure 21 - Methodological steps of the survey (T1.2).....	38
Figure 22 - Evolution of the barriers (T1.2)	39
Figure 23 - Case studies selection criteria.....	39
Figure 24 - Screenshots from different clustering activities and collaborations with EU-funded projects.....	46
Figure 25 - Presentation of SUSTRACK barriers for sustainable living in the context of the Startupper School Academy	47

Figure 26 - Live pictures from different events and exhibition	51
Figure 27 - Co-creation focus group workshop	64
Figure 28 - MIRO board interactive exercise during the co-creation focus group workshop	64
Figure 29 - Registered stakeholders by sector	66
Figure 30 - Registered stakeholders by field	66
Figure 31 - INSPIRE conference agenda	67
Figure 32 - Screenshot of the MIRO boards used during the INSPIRE conference (left: co-creation workshops; right: policy scenario workshops).....	68
Figure 33 - Mentimeter interactive tool for prioritisation of indicators	68
Figure 34 - Summary of prioritized subtopics	69
Figure 35 - Prioritised indicators in the cross-sectorial subtopics	70
Figure 36 - The workshop results have been gathered in MIRO Boards, one for each sector (this figure refers to textile sector).	72
Figure 37 - Other projects and initiatives collaborating with SUSTRACK	74
Figure 38 - Screenshots from the online “Cooperation Launching Event”	77
Figure 39 - Screenshots from the “1st Thematic Discussion Meeting”.....	78
Figure 40 - Screenshots from the 1st MML workshop.....	81
Figure 41 - “Sister project” section on SUSTRACK website	82
Figure 42 - Screenshots from some clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” in which SUSTRACK participated ..	84
Figure 43 - ECOSYSTEMEX initiative.....	85
Figure 44 - Screenshots from different activities with ECOSYSTEMEX	88

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - SUSTRACK Dissemination and communication channels and tools.....	14
Table 2 - List of SUSTRACK publications	20
Table 3 -SUSTRACK followers on LinkedIn and Twitter X.....	30
Table 4 - KPIs foreseen and achieved for dissemination and communication activities	40
Table 5 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: conferences	41
Table 6 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: meetings.....	41
Table 7 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded projects	43
Table 8 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: Education and Training events	46
Table 9 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Events and Exhibitions.....	47
Table 10 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Newsletters	51
Table 11 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Social Media	52
Table 12 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Websites	53
Table 13 - SUSTRACK Stakeholder engagement activities.....	56
Table 14 - The additional policy goals identified by stakeholders during the policy scenario workshop	70
Table 15 - Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM, organised by SUSTRACK	75
Table 16 - Projects identified for collaboration	78
Table 17 - Clustering activities with projects in "Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring", organised by SUSTRACK.....	79
Table 18 - Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”, in which SUSTRACK participated	82
Table 19 - Summary of the activities with ECOSYSTEMEX (not including the dissemination and communication activities)	85

List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
PLRT	Permanent Liaison Round Table
EU	European Union
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
AB	Advisory Board

1 INTRODUCTION

The deliverable D6.1 “Initial Dissemination and Communication plan” provided detailed information about the strategies, methodologies, channels, materials and tools used to support an effective dissemination and communication of the project, together with a tailored stakeholder engagement strategy.

This deliverable, D6.2, reports on the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities from the beginning of the project to M18, with special focus on:

- Dissemination and communication tools and activities implemented;
- Stakeholder engagement activities implemented;
- Collaboration and clustering activities with other relevant projects and initiatives implemented.

FVA, as WP6 leader, and PEDAL, as stakeholder engagement leader, worked in close collaboration with all partners and the coordinators in designing the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement tools and activities, to make sure that all valuable knowledge assets and project’s outputs were identified and properly disseminated/communicated/exploited to engage intended target stakeholders.

This deliverable is divided into 5 main sections:

- Chapter 2 provides an overview of the **dissemination and communication tools** which have been created in the first 18 months of SUSTRACK project;
- Chapter 3 provides an overview of the **dissemination and communication activities** implemented by all partners in the first 18 months of SUSTRACK project;
- Chapter 4 provides an overview of the **stakeholder engagement activities** implemented in the first 18 months of SUSTRACK project, together with a summary of the most successful strategies of stakeholders’ identification and recruitment, a general outline of the organised activities and lessons learnt and recommendation for the second half of the project;
- Chapter 5 provides an overview of the activities implemented in the first 18 months of SUSTRACK project, to foster the **collaboration with relevant projects and initiatives**.
- Finally, Chapter 6 provides conclusions.

2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

To support the Sustrack project dissemination and communication activities, several tools have been designed, based on the strategy defined in D6.1, targeting different target audiences.

A primary and a secondary target audience have been identified in D6.1, to be reached throughout the project, including respectively:

- Primary targets: Policy, Business and financial ecosystem, Research and innovation community, Sustainability system community, Multipliers, Other EU funded projects and initiatives;
- Secondary targets: Civil society, Media.

All the dissemination and communication tools are available for the consortium members in their latest versions on the shared repository, to facilitate easy access.

2.1 Overview of Dissemination and Communication channels and tools

Table 1 lists all the channels and tools envisaged for the project with the KPIs to be achieved, the delivery month (also see D6.1 for detailed information) and the KPIs reached by M18 (in light green background are highlighted the dissemination and communication channels and tools for which the KPIs have been already completed).

Table 1 - Sustrack Dissemination and communication channels and tools

OVERVIEW OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS				
Category	Channel/Tool	KPIs	KPI Reached	Target Audience
Brand identity	Brand identity kit (Logo, Templates, Guidelines)	#1 (M1)	#1 (M1)	All target audiences
Sustrack Website	Website	#1 (M3) with >10,000 visits from >25 countries	#1 (M1) with 23822 unique visitors from >105 countries (last update: 23/04/2024)	All target audiences
Promotional material	Flyers	#2, 500 distributed (M6-M24)	#1, 25 distributed	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets

	Roll-ups	#2 (M6, M24)	#1	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Posters	>2 (M6, M24)	In accordance with the coordination team, the poster will be created later, to disseminate results	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Presentations about the project and its achievements	On demand	#1	All target audiences
Publications and actionable knowledge	Publications	>6	#6 (in progress)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Case study factsheets (one per each sector)	At least #4	Not started yet.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Conference outcome factsheets	#3	#1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Case studies videos (one per each sector)	At least #4	Not started yet.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainability system community
	Infographic cards	#20	Not started yet.	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Toolkits to make the actionable knowledge easily accessible to the stakeholders in the 6 target countries (IT, NL, SK, DE, BE, ES)	#6 (1 per country) + #1 in English	Not started yet.	Mainly primary targets in the 6 target countries
Multimedia	Promotional video	#1 (M8)	#1 (M1)	All target audiences
	Video teasers for Social Media campaigns	#2	#1	All target audiences
	Promotional banners	>10	#5	All target audiences
	Thematic cards	#10	#7	All target audiences
Dissemination and communication materials	Email campaigns	#10	#5	All target audiences
	Newsletters	>3 (M12, M24, M36)	#1 (M12)	All target audiences
	Press releases	>4 (M1, M12, M24, M36)	#2 (M1, M12)	All target audiences
Social Media	<p>Social Media profiles (LinkedIn, Twitter X)</p> <p>Additional: YouTube</p>	#2 (M3), >3000 followers, >1000 posts	#3 (M1), 425 followers, 133 post (last update: 23/04/2024)	All target audiences

	Social Media campaigns	>4	#2	All target audiences
--	------------------------	----	----	----------------------

2.2 Brand identity kit

A recognisable visual identity was designed and produced at the early stage of the project’s course. Detailed information about the brand identity kit was delivered in D6.1.

2.3 Website

The first version of the [SUSTRACK website](#) was designed and deployed on M1. Detailed information about its design was already delivered in D6.1. During the first 18 months of the project, SUSTRACK website was visited by 23822 unique visitors from >105 countries (last update 23/04/2024).

Additional sections were added in M17 and M18, in order to enrich the structure of the website and to convey new information, following the project’s progress. The new sections are described below.

2.3.1 “Advisory board” section

The [“Advisory board” section](#) was added under the “About” main menu (Figure 1). In this section, all the members of SUSTRACK Advisory Board (AB) are publicly presented, including the following information: name, surname, position and affiliations, brief biography, link to their LinkedIn profile.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the “Advisory Board” section on SUSTRACK website

2.3.2 “Outcomes” section

The “Outcomes” section (Figure 2) has been added to the main menu of SUSTRACK website, in order to collect in an organized and easily accessible manner all the results and outcomes of the SUSTRACK project as it progresses.

4 subsections are currently included under the “Outcomes” section:

- [Case studies](#)
- [Conference factsheets](#)
- [Press release](#)
- [Newsletter](#)

Additional items such as deliverables, publications, and all other relevant results will be added later on.

Figure 2 - Screenshot of the "Outcomes" section on SUSTRACK website

2.3.3 News page

The "News" section (Figure 3) was constantly updated, in order to have an overview of the main activities, achievements, conferences and events organised by SUSTRACK, and in which SUSTRACK partners proactively participated. Moreover, press releases and newsletters are also published in this section, maximising their diffusion through this channel.

The news are also systematically published on all the social media channels to increase their impact and views.

Figure 3 - Screenshots of the "News" section on SUSTRACK website

2.4 Flyers

A first version of the flyer, presenting the SUSTRACK project, has been designed at M6. Detailed information was delivered in D6.1.

25 flyers have been distributed during two large-scale events held in Italy (Figure 4) described in detail in Section 3.3.1 (EU Researchers Night 2023 and Maker Faire 2023).

As a general rule, partners are encouraged to limit the printing of any promotional materials, following the paperless guidelines recommended by the European Commission.

Figure 4 - SUSTRACK flyers distribution in Researchers Night 2023

2.5 Roll-ups

A first version of the **roll-up**, presenting the SUSTRACK project, has been designed at M5. Detailed information was delivered in D6.1.

The roll-up is used to promote the project in conferences and events where the partners participate.

2.6 Posters

In accordance with the coordinator UNITELMA, the poster was not delivered at M6: posters will be created to convey specific results, and not general information about SUSTRACK, which are already covered by Roll-ups and Flyers.

2.7 Project presentation

A **Power Point presentation** about the project and its achievements (including objectives, expected outcomes...) has been designed at M5, ready to be customised by partners depending on the purpose. Detailed information was included in D6.1.

2.8 Publications

Although **publications** are not the main objective, being SUSTRACK a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, some partners have some publications in progress, deriving from the results of different tasks (Table 2).

Table 2 - List of SUSTRACK publications

Task	Authors	Title	Journal	Status
------	---------	-------	---------	--------

T1.1	Elina Dace, Alessandro Cascavilla, Marco Bianchi, Elisa Chioatto, Emy Zecca, Luana Ladu, Gülşah Yilan	The Barriers to Transition to Circular Bio-based Economy: Findings from the Grey Literature Analysis	Sustainable Production and Consumption	Under review
T2.1	Marco Bianchi, Alessandro Cascavilla, Janire Clavell Diaz, Luana Ladu, Barbara Palacino Blazquez, Menger Pierre, Eleonora Staffieri, Gülşah Yilan	Research gaps and future directions in monitoring and modelling the transition to a circular bioeconomy: a review	Sustainable Production and Consumption	Under review
T1.2	Gülşah Yilan, Elina Dace, Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu, Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini, Gabor Mester, Piergiuseppe Morone	Mapping the Barriers to a Sustainable Transition: Insights from an Extensive Grey Literature Analysis and Focus Group Discussion	Conference paper (SDEWES 2024 Conference)	Accepted for presentation
T1.2	Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu	Assessing the Impact of Digital Product Passports on the Transition to a Circular Bio-based Economy	Conference paper (Eu-SPRI 2024 Conference)	Abstract accepted; paper in progress
T1.2	Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu	Exploring the Potential of Digital Product Passports for establishing a Circular Bio-based Economy: the Role of Standardisation	Conference paper (EURAS 2024 Conference)	Paper draft submitted
T3.3	Joris Van Acker, Liselotte De Ligne, Tobi Hallez, Jan Van den Bulcke	Engineered wood products for construction based on beech and poplar resources in Europe	Conference paper (Hardwood 2024 Conference)	Keynote, Paper draft submitted

2.9 Case study factsheets

An extensive preliminary version of the case study factsheets has been delivered in D3.1. These factsheets contain valuable information that will serve as the foundation for creating visually

appealing final versions, which will be produced once the task is completed and the final case studies (with data and information nurturing the factsheets) will be selected.

FVA, as dissemination and communication leader, is now involving all partners into a discussion on the best way to organise the materials available, with the aim of transforming them into actionable knowledge for target stakeholders.

Since this work will be done in a later stage of the project, in the meantime, FVA is planning to develop sector-specific factsheets to be launched through a dedicated social media campaign. These factsheets will include the name of the sector, limits, challenges and impacts of the actual linear fossil-based economy, promising applications (Sustrack case studies title and scores per selection criteria), barriers to the uptake of bio-based solutions, and proposed policy actions. All partners will be involved in collecting the relevant information. This campaign is scheduled for launch before the summer of 2024.

2.10 Conference outcome factsheets

A factsheet to report the main takeaways from the INSPIRE conference has been created after a deep analysis of the results obtained, thanks to the proactive collaboration of partners (Figure 5). The factsheet includes the following information:

- Brief introduction of Sustrack;
- Objectives and format of the INSPIRE conference;
- Participant information (sectors and fields);
- Main results from co-creation workshops;
- Main results from policy scenario workshops.

This factsheet has been shared both on the [Sustrack website](#) and on social media ([Twitter X](#) [LinkedIn](#)) to maximize its dissemination and impact, reaching 518 views (last update: 23/04/2024).

Figure 5 -Two pages of the INSPIRE Conference factsheet

2.11 Case studies videos

The 4 case studies videos will be produced in a later phase of the project, once the related task is completed and the final case studies (with data and information) are selected. FVA will involve all partners into a discussion, in order to understand which case studies to select for this activity, and which information to convey and share with the target stakeholders (e.g., these videos can support/complement/reinforce the abovementioned case study factsheets, also involving the companies mentioned, e.g. through interviews).

2.12 Infographic cards

Infographic cards providing technical information and data on general questions (e.g., connected to LCA, monitoring the transition, impacts) will be produced in a later stage of the project, in connection with WP2 results. Some of these outcomes are already available, however they are pending publication: thus, FVA plans to disseminate and disclose them once the publication(s) are accepted.

2.13 Toolkits

7 toolkits, in the 6 languages of the target countries (IT, NL, SK, DE, BE, ES) and 1 in English, will be created in the latest stage of the project, to package outcomes as actionable knowledge to

facilitate exploitation and adoption by stakeholders and beyond, and maximise the impact of the project and the awareness of the main target audiences.

2.14 Promotional video

A [Promotional video](#) of the project was designed and produced in M1, with the aim of explaining in a comprehensible and attractive way the SUSTRACK objectives, target beneficiaries and expected outcomes (Figure 6). It has been used to open SUSTRACK events, such as the “SUSTRACK co-creation focus group workshop” and the INSPIRE conference. Moreover, it has been shown at the ECOSYSTEX conference (see Section 3.2 for details) and by partners in their communication activities.

The video is also accessible from the SUSTRACK website, as well as on the SUSTRACK YouTube and Social Media channels.

Figure 6 - Screenshot of the SUSTRACK promotional video

2.15 Video teasers for social media campaigns

The first of the two video teasers was already designed, in collaboration with the BAM partner. [The video](#) was shot in the framework of the EU Green Week, since SUSTRACK was a partner of the event with the organisation of the “SUSTRACK co-creation focus group workshop” (Figure 7).

In detail, these audio-visual materials were kindly requested by the organisers of the EU Green Week, in order to further promote partners’ events. They used these products on the Social Media platforms of DG ENV ([reposted by SUSTRACK](#)) and on the [EU Green Week website](#).

Figure 7 - Screenshot of the first Sustrack video teaser

2.16 Promotional banners

Promotional banners play an important role in the digital promotion of Sustrack and its activities across social media platforms. These banners serve as visual representations of core messages, capturing attention and conveying them effectively.

5 main promotional banners have been shared on Sustrack social media (Figure 8), in order to both promote project's activities and events, driving interest and participation from diverse audiences, and to keep the target audience engaged. In particular, they have been produced to:

- Promote the Sustrack survey (T1.2.2);
- Promote the INSPIRE conference;
- Promote the Sustrack co-creation focus group workshop;
- Celebrate World Water Day 2023: as part of the [UN World Water Day](#) activities, Sustrack was invited to post to present the project itself and to adhere to a campaign organised by DG RTD;
- Celebrate Winter break.

Figure 8 - Promotional banners shared on SUSTRACK social media

2.17 Thematic cards

Thematic cards are aimed to convey content (both general and connected to the four specific sectors) in order to inform and educate all target audiences.

A first set of 7 thematic cards (Figure 9) has been created and launched on social media to promote SUSTRACK research. In particular, these cards unveiled the categorisation of barriers hindering the transition to a circular, low-carbon, bio-based economy into the six dimensions (cultural, economic, environmental, governance, structural, and technical) identified in WP1 work (further described in Section 2.22.2).

Figure 9 - Thematic cards used for the “Cluster of barriers” social media campaign

2.18 Email campaigns

Email campaigns served as indispensable tools within SUSTRACK, facilitating direct communication with stakeholders and fostering their active participation in project’s events and activities. By leveraging this strategy, SUSTRACK effectively reached stakeholders across the four different sectors (textile, construction, plastics, chemicals) and geographical regions, cultivating a sense of involvement and ownership among stakeholders. These email campaigns were meticulously crafted to deliver targeted messages, personally providing relevant updates, invitations, and opportunities for engagement to stakeholders. As a result, these campaigns played a pivotal role in forging connections, nurturing collaboration, and driving the success of SUSTRACK activities and events, by harnessing the power of direct communication.

In particular, thanks to the collaboration of all partners, 5 main email campaigns have been launched by SUSTRACK, regarding:

- SUSTRACK survey (T1.2.2);
- INSPIRE conference;
- SUSTRACK co-creation focus group workshop;
- SUSTRACK Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop;
- First SUSTRACK newsletter.

2.19 Newsletters

The first newsletter (Figure 10) was distributed via email and promoted on 31 October 2024 on the [SUSTRACK website](#) and Social Media platforms ([Twitter X](#) [LinkedIn](#)), reaching 737 stakeholders through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download from SUSTRACK website - last update 23/04/2024). We included in the newsletter:

- SUSTRACK INSPIRE conference program;
- SUSTRACK research results about:
 - Limits, barriers and solutions to boost the transition towards a circular bio-based economy;
 - How can the transition to circular bio-based systems be monitored and evaluated?
 - Case studies selection;
 - Generation of a policy portfolio scenario.
- SUSTRACK participation at European Researchers' Night and Maker Faire in Italy;
- How to be involved in collaboration with other projects and initiatives in the bioeconomy innovation system.

Figure 10 - Screenshots of two pages of the newsletter

2.20 Press releases

A first press release was distributed and promoted on 8 February 2023 on the [Sustrack website](#), Social Media platforms ([Twitter X](#) [LinkedIn](#)) and through partners’ Press Offices. We included in the Press Release the kick-off of the project and the specific ongoing activities.

A second press release was distributed and promoted on 31 October 2024 on the [Sustrack website](#), Social Media platforms ([Twitter X](#) [LinkedIn](#)) and through partners’ Press Offices, reaching 406 stakeholders through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download from Sustrack website - last update 23/04/2024). We included in the Press Release the main results from the first 12 months, such as limits, barriers and solutions to boost the transition towards a circular bio-based economy, monitoring and evaluation of the transition to circular bio-based systems; case studies selection, generation of policy portfolio scenario.

Partners distributed the press releases among their networks.

Both press releases reached more than 400 stakeholders, through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download from Sustrack website - last update 23/04/2024).

2.21 Social media profiles

The official Social Network pages of the project ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter X](#)) have been created and launched at M1, together with the website launch. Detailed information was delivered in D6.1. Sustrack uses social media as one of the main channels to reach its stakeholders, and in particular research centres and universities, companies, B2B industries, European projects, institutional bodies and policy makers.

Twitter X and LinkedIn, addressing a more professional audience compared to other social media channel as Facebook and Instagram, have been chosen to:

- Inform about the project’s results, outcomes, and activities;
- Publish information about events the project is organising, with the aim to involve and engage stakeholders;
- Promote interesting external news and articles related to Sustrack and the Bioeconomy field in general.

Table 3 offers a specific overview of the Sustrack followers per each social media channel.

Table 3 -Sustrack followers on LinkedIn and Twitter X

LinkedIn	
Followers	282
Link	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sustrack/
Twitter X	
Followers	143
Link	https://twitter.com/SUSTRACK_eu

Thanks to the social media animation, SUSTRACK channels keep growing, counting now in total 425 followers. Currently, more than 130 posts (Figure 11), with different formats and contents (banners, videos, photos, thematic cards, images, thematic cards...), have been published to engage the target audiences. In fact, successful social media communication is based around a combination of frequent, topical, relevant, open, authentic, creative and innovative content and dialogue. According to the shared plan for the social media channels developed (see D6.1), SUSTRACK social media channels are animated with a variety of contents including project’s activities, events and results, insights from deliverables, articles, news, information from the Bioeconomy field.

Figure 11 - Examples of social media posts

Contrary to initial expectations outlined in the Grant Agreement, the large public is not the appropriate target audience to prioritise for the SUSTRACK project, as already depicted in D6.1 (Section 2.3): Civil society/citizens & Media were identified as secondary targets for dissemination and communication.

Consequently, the expected number of posts and followers we anticipate reaching by the end of the project will be narrower than initially envisaged during the proposal preparation phase. Nonetheless, now that more tangible results are emerging from SUSTRACK, we will certainly take action to enhance our social media presence with increased frequency and disseminate/communicate as much relevant content as possible (including new formats e.g., infographics, factsheet), tailored to SUSTRACK primary targets, in order to boost engagement.

2.22 Social media campaigns

2.22.1 “INSPIRE Conference” social media campaign

The social media campaign for the INSPIRE conference aimed to promote the event and attract the attention of potentially interested stakeholders, encouraging their registration, through dedicated cards (Figure 12).

The campaign strategy focused on highlighting the unique insights and innovations presented at the INSPIRE Conference, as well as the relevance and significance of their contributions to stakeholders. In particular, partners who presented results during the conference, including UNITELMA (project manager and coordinator), as well as representatives from BAM, TECNALIA, WR, DBFZ, and KE, provided a quote, specifically addressing the question: "What's in for stakeholders? Why is the INSPIRE conference of interest for them and what's new?". Each quote was accompanied by a picture of the "speaker", enhancing the visual appeal and engagement of the social media posts.

SUSTRACK

Participating in this "inspiring conference" will provide you with the opportunity to have your say on what is really important for promoting a sustainable transition! It takes a strong and collective effort to address the global challenges we are facing and no one is exempt from it!

Prof. PIERGIUSEPPE MORONE
Project Coordinator,
UnitelmaSapienza University of Rome

Funded by the European Union

INSPIRE CONFERENCE

SUSTRACK

We invite you to get a deeper understanding of what hinders the transition to a circular bioeconomy and have your saying on what matters the most in your area of expertise.

GLSAH YILAN
Project Manager, UnitelmaSapienza
University of Rome

Funded by the European Union

INSPIRE CONFERENCE

SUSTRACK

You will gain the chance to get valuable insights into the most recent developments shared by key stakeholders concerning the most pressing barriers and gaps that hinder the transition of four critical sectors towards a sustainable circular bio-economy.

LUANA LADU
German Federal Institute for Material
Research and Testing (BAM)

Funded by the European Union

INSPIRE CONFERENCE

SUSTRACK

We cannot improve what we cannot measure. That is why our mission is to improve the means to evaluate and monitor progress towards a circular bioeconomy and encourage its application.

MARCO BIANCHI
Senior researcher, Fundacion
TECNALIA Research & Innovation

Funded by the European Union

INSPIRE CONFERENCE

SUSTRACK

You will gain invaluable insights on how qualitative and quantitative models connect sectoral actions to strategic national development objectives, fueling innovation and shaping a brighter, greener future.

GEORG PALLASKE
Knowledge Sil

Funded by the European Union

INSPIRE CONFERENCE

SUSTRACK

We show you possible ways of how more ambitious policy objectives might support the transition to a sustainable and circular bioeconomy in Europe.

NORA SZARKA
DBFZ - Deutsches
Biomasseforschungszentrum gGmbH

Funded by the European Union

INSPIRE CONFERENCE

Figure 12 -Cards used for the “INSPIRE conference” social media campaign

This campaign reached 4163 views, 231 reactions, 36 repost on LinkedIn and 479 views, 16 likes, 5 retweets on Twitter X (last update: 23/04/2024).

2.22.2 “Cluster of barriers” social media campaign

The social media campaign “Cluster of barriers” (Figure 13) aimed to:

- tease a future social media campaign presenting in details the barriers hindering the transition to a circular, low-carbon, bio-based economy, which SUSTRACK is currently identifying and prioritizing in WP1 work;
- maintain stakeholders engaged in social media while collecting the above-mentioned final results;
- attract new followers to the social media channels.

The set of 7 thematic cards used for this social media campaign is reported in Section 2.17. These cards unveiled the categorisation of the barriers into six dimensions identified in WP1 work, namely:

- 1) Cultural barriers: consumer behaviour, perception, attitude, awareness, consumption trends and traditions, workers’ skills, qualifications, education, age and gender, internal culture, processes, attitudes, actions, and governance of companies.
- 2) Technical barriers: technology development, innovation and adoption, infrastructure capacity, quality and quantity of feedstock, composition of materials, digitalisation and automation.
- 3) Economic barriers: costs incurred on a company, profitability, competitiveness, access to funding and investment, product’s market share, demand, and price.
- 4) Environmental barriers: environmental performance of products and processes, environmental impact assessment.
- 5) Governance barriers: policy, regulation, policy targets, incentives, standards, certification schemes, and standardisation and certification procedures.
- 6) Structural barriers: systemic institutional barriers, practices and norms, overall persisting systemic issues and regimes, and the complexity of systems.

Figure 13 - A couple of screenshots of the “Cluster of barriers” social media campaign

This campaign reached 1881 views, 63 reactions, 7 repost on LinkedIn and 281 views, 10 likes, 2 retweets on Twitter X (last update: 23/04/2024).

2.23 Other graphical materials

As the dissemination and communication leader, FVA was also responsible for the graphical design of interactive tools and dissemination/communication materials for deliverables, presentations, publications, ensuring alignment with project objectives, brand identity, and stakeholder preferences.

Regarding the design of interactive tools used during project’s events such as the co-creation focus group and INSPIRE conference (such as MIRO Board), screenshots and details are reported in Chapter 4. In general, the design of these tools was meticulously crafted in collaboration with partners, in order to integrate research needs and questions, optimisation of usability and visual appeal, as well as ensuring the engagement of stakeholders.

Regarding the design of dissemination/communication materials, they were developed to support partners and answer their specific requests and needs. These materials were included in products such as deliverables, publications, presentations, and the design principles focused on:

- Visual Coherence: All communication materials adhered to SUSTRACK brand identity guidelines (e.g., use of colours, fonts, etc.);
- Clarity and Readability: Graphical elements were designed with readability in mind, employing appropriate font sizes, spacing, and contrast to enhance content legibility and comprehension;

- Visual Impact: Eye-catching visuals were incorporated to capture audience attention and convey complex information in a clear and engaging manner.

A selection of the materials developed is listed below.

- 1) Methodology of the Sustrack co-creation focus group workshop. This graphic (Figure 14) was included in the SDEWES conference paper.

Figure 14 - Methodology of the Sustrack co-creation focus group workshop

- 2) Screening criteria for the identification of policy goals and Biotransition, Biorevolution scenarios' icons, used in D4.1 and also in subsequent interactive tools and presentations and in the interactive tools (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Screening criteria for the identification of policy goals and Biotransition, Biorevolution scenarios' icons

- 3) Visualisation of the circular biobased economy (CBBE) definition, used in WP5 policy brief (Figure 16).

Figure 16 - Visualisation of the CBBE definition

4) Several figures produced for D1.2 (detailed description in Figures 17-22 captions), and used also in subsequent presentations.

Figure 17 - Timeline of task T1.2

Figure 18 - Identification and consolidation process of the barriers to a CBBE (T1.2)

Figure 19 - Methodological steps of the interviews (T1.2)

Figure 20 - Primary and secondary objectives of interviews (T1.2)

Figure 21 - Methodological steps of the survey (T1.2)

Figure 22 - Evolution of the barriers (T1.2)

5) D3.1 Selection criteria for case studies, used in D3.1 (Figure 23).

Figure 23 - Case studies selection criteria

3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In SUSTRACK, various dissemination and communication activities were undertaken through collaborative efforts among all partners. Below (Table 4) is a brief summary of the KPIs foreseen and achieved, while detailed descriptions of individual activities are provided in the subsequent sections.

Table 4 - KPIs foreseen and achieved for dissemination and communication activities

Activity	KPIs	KPI Reached
Talks at events and conferences (live and online)	>10	2 Conferences, 20 participants 9 Dissemination events in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded project , 363 participants
Meetings with stakeholders	>40 participants reached	7 Meetings, 240 participants
Direct and indirect reach of SUSTRACK primary and secondary target audience	At least 10,000 stakeholders directly and indirectly in total (among them 500 primary targets reached indirectly through communication and dissemination activities)	2 Education and training lectures, 410 participants 6 Events and Exhibitions, 1495 participants Newsletters, 600 recipients Social Media, >10000 followers reached (also through partners' channels)

Other activities involving actively the stakeholders (primary target audience), such as thematic webinars, capacity building, co-creation and foresight exercises are reported in Chapter 4. Those activities are pivotal not only for stakeholder engagement, but also for strengthening the dissemination and communication of the project's results.

3.1 Dissemination activities

SUSTRACK partners performed several dissemination activities during the first 18 months of the project, by participating as speakers in various conferences and workshops, by providing education and training to schools and universities, but also by collaborating with other EU-funded projects and initiatives. Meetings with stakeholders were also organised in order to present SUSTRACK results.

The following sections describe the dissemination activities undertaken to reach the different target stakeholders.

3.1.1 Conferences

KE partner participated into 2 conferences to present SUSTRACK results. Further details are reported in Table 5.

Table 5 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: conferences

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
KE	09/01/2024: Presentation of the modelling work being carried out in SUSTRACK, with a conversation on its use for innovation. During this event, interest was raised within the EC to explore the use of System Dynamics in more detail.	EU institutions (European Commission: DG Research & Innovation)	10 online participants
KE	01/03/2024: Main speaker at the event “Coffeenomics with Andrea Bassi: System Dynamics-GEM-circular economy”. Presentation of the System Dynamics work, including the creation of sectoral industry models, and their integration in the Green Economy Model (GEM) in SUSTRACK.	EU institutions (European Commission: DG Research & Innovation, specifically Unit G1 "Common R&I Strategy and Foresight Service")	10 online participants, but the meeting was recorded and shared further by the EC

3.1.2 Meetings

SUSTRACK partners participated to several meetings to disseminate SUSTRACK results. Further details are reported in Table 6.

Table 6 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: meetings

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
KE	15/03/2024: Conversation on the use of System Dynamics modelling for SUSTRACK on the topic of innovation, with Bianca Cavicchi (DG Research & Innovation) and	European Commission: DG Research & Innovation	3 online participants

	Igor Oliveira (Technical University of Denmark).		
BAM	28/02/2024: Presentation of T1.2 results during the Circular Economy Jour Fixe (cross-departmental BAM internal meeting)	BAM researchers working on Circular Economy related topics	13 participants
BAM	16/03/2023: Presentation of the SUSTRACK project during the Focus Area Day Environment through a poster during the poster session of the event and networking with researchers for T3.1 (identifying case studies)	Annual BAM networking event (mainly visited by BAM researchers, but also open to and visited by other German research institutions)	Not measured, yearly ca. 100 visitors
BAM	14/03/2024: Presentation of the results of T1.2 during the Focus Area Day Environment through a poster during the poster session of the event	Annual BAM networking event (mainly visited by BAM researchers, but also open to and visited by other German research institutions)	Not measured; yearly ca. 100 visitors
DBFZ	14/12/2024: Presentation of T4.1 aims and results during quarterly Bioenergy systems department meeting.	Quarterly internal meeting among working groups of the Bioenergy systems department.	Not measured
WR	22/08/2023; 11/09/2023: Interviews were held with, to retrieve input for the waste-to-methanol case study analysis. SUSTRACK was presented during these interviews as well.	Several prominent players in the field of sustainable chemicals (i.e. Air Liquide, Enkern and Lowlands Methanol BV).	7 Total interviewees
UGENT	Presentation of the SUSTRACK project during meetings of two regional projects (Flanders), namely “VLAIO Living Lab Hennep+” and “Brabantse Wouden als Circulair Hout Platform (BWCHP)”, relevant to Case Study 1 and 3.	Research communities Industry, business partners Innovators Investors	16 participants

3.2 Dissemination activities in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded projects

SUSTRACK partners disseminated several SUSTRACK results in the context of clustering activities and collaboration with other EU-Funded projects and initiatives (Figure 24). Further details are reported in Table 7.

Table 7 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded projects

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA	24/01/2023: Presentation of SUSTRACK project at the first ECOSYSTEMEX - European Community of Practice for a Sustainable Textile Ecosystem workshop.	Research communities Industry, business partners Innovators Investors EU institutions Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	55 online participants
UNITELMA	14/04/2023: Presentation of SUSTRACK project and its stakeholder engagement activities (namely focus group of T1.2.1) in the “ECOSYSTEMEX Dissemination Webinar #4”.	Research communities Industry, business partners Innovators Investors EU institutions Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	45 online participants Projects represented: Glaukos, GRETE, CIRPASS, S4Fashion, HackThatFashion
UNITELMA	28/06/2023: Presentation of SUSTRACK project and discussion of the preliminary results of Gap Analysis and Focus Group Workshop regarding the identified limits and barriers (WP1), in “The Biocircularcities Trilogy - Episode 1: Supporting local players with the transition to circular bioeconomy, and lifting the current barriers”.	Research communities Industry, business partners National Authorities Civil society and Citizens	30 online participants

FVA	22/09/2023: Presentation and promotion of SUSTRACK INSPIRE conference at “ The 5th ECOSYSTEEX Insight Series ”.	Research communities Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	40 online participants
UNITELMA, FVA	18-20/10/2023: SUSTRACK project video was projected in the plenary room during lunch and coffee breaks at the ECOSYSTEEX conference, held in Barcelona, Spain, on 18-20 October 2023.	Research communities Industry, business partners Innovators Investors EU institutions Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	100 onsite participants
FVA	27/11/2023: Presentation of SUSTRACK project and some preliminary results during the “CBE JU communication thematic group”.	EU institutions Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	20 online representatives of 30 projects
BAM, FVA	12/12/2023: Presentation of WP1 results on barriers hindering the transition and dissemination of SUSTRACK survey in the “ECOSYSTEEX TG4 - Renewable Materials & Standards” working group.	Research communities Industry, business partners Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	7 online participants
UNITELMA, FVA	08/03/2024: Presentation of SUSTRACK multistep, multi-stakeholder approach for identifying and consolidating the barriers for the transition to a circular biobased economy SUSTRACK at “ The 8th ECOSYSTEEX Insight Series ”.	Research communities Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	67 online participants
BAM	28/02/2024: Explored a potential collaboration with	Research communities	1 participant

	<p>fellow BAM researchers working on the EU Horizon project IMPACTIVE (Innovative Mechanochemical Processes to synthesise green ACTIVE pharmaceutical ingredients). Several topics were presented: Sustrack project, the sectors, the case studies, the sustainability indicators and monitoring tools. Further alignment meetings are foreseen.</p>		
TECNALIA	<p>18/01/2023: Linking of Sustrack with CCRI (Circular Cities and Regions Initiative), an initiative under the EU Circular Economy Action Plan) and integration of Sustrack into the CCRI database of relevant HEU projects of interest for the CCRI</p>	<p>Research communities Policy makers at local level (regions and cities) SMEs Investors</p>	<p>The CCRI mobilises directly +70 core associated organisations (PILOTS, FELLOWS, Associated Partners, CCRI projects)</p>

Figure 24 - Screenshots from different clustering activities and collaborations with EU-funded projects

3.2.1 Education and Training events

FVA partner organised 2 education and training events, disseminating Sustrack results both to research communities in academic context, and to high school students and teachers. Further details are reported in Table 8.

Table 8 - Sustrack Dissemination activities: Education and Training events

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA	01/03/2023: Lecture in the context of the course in Geographic and Territorial processes, at University of Bologna. Sustrack project and its monitoring activities on the four most carbon-intensive sectors, specifically on construction sector, were presented during the lecture.	Research communities	30 online participants
FVA	21/11/2023: Presentation of Sustrack results about the barriers to the transition for sustainable living, in the context of the Startupper School Academy (Figure 25).	High school students and teachers	380 participants

Figure 25 - Presentation of SUSTRACK barriers for sustainable living in the context of the Startupper School Academy

3.3 Communication activities

SUSTRACK partners performed several communication activities during the first 18 months of the project, by organising and participating in events and exhibitions, but also promoting the project online (e.g., via social media, websites).

The following sections describe the communication activities undertaken to reach the different target stakeholders.

3.3.1 Event and Exhibition

SUSTRACK partners participated in several events and exhibitions to communicate about the project, its activities and related topics (Figure 26). Further details are reported in Table 9.

Table 9 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Events and Exhibitions

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA, UNITELMA, PEDAL	05/10/2022: SUSTRACK was presented in the context of the “Projects2Projects” Mobilisation and Mutual learning workshop , in Brussels (GA already signed). During the event, Knowledge exchange among ongoing H2020 projects and new Horizon Europe projects supporting the bioeconomy. SUSTRACK was presented by Gülşah Yılan. Brussels. identified synergies among similar projects under	Research communities	Around 60 onsite participants (40 projects involved on stage and additional 9 projects participating)

	standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring cluster		
FVA, UNITELMA	11/10/2022: On the occasion of the Festival dello Sviluppo Sostenibile 2022 (Sustainable Development Festival 2022, Rome, in Italian), promoted by ASviS - Italian Alliance for Sustainable Development, "The green transition between training, innovation and standards" seminar was held to present the European and non-European projects in which UNITELMA and FVA participates as a partner or of which they are the leader. SUSTRACK (GA already signed) was presented by Piergiuseppe Morone and the scientific community was informed about the ongoing research related to standards and ecolabels for the bioeconomy.	Research communities	40 onsite participants
PEDAL	17/08/2023: SUSTRACK project was presented at a national workshop aimed to furnish policymakers with a comprehensive overview of the involvement of Slovak partners in the HORIZON 2020 and HORIZON Europe projects, in Nitra, Slovakia. National Agricultural Policy makers were informed about SUSTRACK project and its upcoming events and activities.	National authorities	5 onsite participants
FVA, UNITELMA	29-30/09/2023: Together with other EU-funded projects (GenB , BlueMissionMed), SUSTRACK organised quiz and games to talk about bioeconomy, circular economy, sustainability and impacts assessment at the European	Citizens	300 onsite participants

	<p>Researchers' Night 2023 in Frascati (Rome).</p> <p>UNITELMA prepared a "bottle game" for the comparison of a conventional plastic and a reusable bioplastic bottle to stimulate a discussion about sustainability performance in terms of economic, environmental and social aspects. We underlined the challenges to assess the sustainability performance and refer to our project's objectives to highlight the importance of the transition to a better circular biobased economy model.</p>		
FVA, UNITELMA	<p>20-22/10/2023: Together with other EU-funded projects (GenB, BlueMissionMed), SUSTRACK organised quiz and games to talk about bioeconomy, circular economy, sustainability and impacts assessment at Maker Faire 2023 in Rome.</p> <p>UNITELMA played the "bottle game" described above.</p>	Citizens	1000 onsite participants
FVA, UNITELMA	<p>14/03/2024: SUSTRACK was promoted during the "Bioeconomy Changemakers festival 2024 - Rome edition", in particular during the sessions dedicated to Career Talks, in which a representative from UNITELMA had a pitch and FVA representatives promoted the project among participants.</p>	High school students and teachers	90 onsite participants

Figure 26 - Live pictures from different events and exhibition

3.3.2 Promotion of SUSTRACK in external Newsletters

SUSTRACK project and its activities were promoted in 4 external newsletters, thanks to partners' networks and efforts. Further details are reported in Table 10.

Table 10 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Newsletters

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
------------	------------------------------------	-----------------	--------

UNITELMA, FVA	21/09/2023: SUSTRACK INSPIRE conference promotion in Biocircularcities newsletter	Primary target audience	480 recipients
PEDAL	28/11/2023: SUSTRACK INSPIRE conference promotion in Circular Slovakia monthly newsletter	Industry, business partners	Not measured
FVA	21/12/2023: SUSTRACK website promotion in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED newsletter	Primary target audience	115 recipients
DBFZ	Promotion of INSPIRE conference in partner Newsletter	Primary target audience	Not measured

3.3.3 Promotion of SUSTRACK in partners' and other Social Media

SUSTRACK project and its activities were promoted in partners' social media, which reposted and diffused several contents published by the official project's channels. Notably, SUSTRACK contents were also promoted/diffused by other social media channels (e.g., ECOSYSTEMEX). All details are reported in Table 11.

Table 11 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Social Media

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
UNITELMA, FVA, PEDAL, TECNALIA, CIRCE, KE, UNIFE, WR	Partners, reposted several contents published by SUSTRACK project, during the overall duration of the first 18 months.	All target audience	<p>UNITELMA and personal profiles 3000 followers</p> <p>FVA, EuBioNet and personal profiles 1000 followers</p> <p>PEDAL 1489 followers</p> <p>TECNALIA 839 followers</p>

			<p>CIRCE 1500 followers</p> <p>KE and personal profiles 500 followers</p> <p>UNIFE 1707 followers</p>
FVA	February 2024: SUSTRACK presentation in the LinkedIn group “Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU BioEconomy” .	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	892 views, 12 reactions (last updated: 23/04/2024)
FVA	Promotion of SUSTRACK events on ECOSYSTEMEX social media, during the overall duration of the first 18 months (once the collaboration with ECOSYSTEMEX started).	Primary target audiences	Not measured

3.3.4 Promotion of SUSTRACK in partners’ website

SUSTRACK project was promoted in several partners’ websites. Details are reported in Table 12.

Table 12 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Websites

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA	Dedicated website section about project information	Specific user communities	390 visitors (last update: 23/04/2024)
PEDAL	Dedicated website section about project information	Specific user communities	Not measured
UNITELMA	Announcement of SUSTRACK with video teaser in UNITELMA BIT website	Specific user communities	Not measured

BAM	Project’s website linked on BAM’s website reporting about circular economy activities	BAM website visitors	Not measured
DBFZ	Project’s website linked on DBFZ’s subpage for the Working Group Biomass in Energy Systems	DBFZ website visitors	Not measured
UNIFE	Dedicated article on UNIFE website	UNIFE website visitors	Not measured

3.4 Lessons learnt and recommendation for the second half of the project

While during the first Reporting Period, most of communication (and dissemination) activities were devoted to promote the project’s objectives, for the second Reporting Period, when the SUSTRACK project results will be more mature, the activities will be focused on creating and disseminating Actionable Knowledge out of them. For this reason, FVA will work with the partners in order to identify the key results that can be transformed into valuable materials, to be shared with stakeholders and the large public. These materials will be used to nurture social media channels and increase SUSTRACK impacts.

4 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Stakeholder engagement is one of the main pillars of the SUSTRACK project, since the involvement of stakeholders throughout all the project's WPs ensures that the project outcomes are shared and validated among relevant target audiences. The main objective of the stakeholder engagement activities is to connect stakeholder feedback with the project results, considering all perspectives.

4.1 Continuous identification and involvement of SUSTRACK project stakeholders

Several recruitment strategies, described in detail in D6.1, have been implemented for the identification and involvement of stakeholders during the first 18 months of SUSTRACK project.

- Direct invitation of relevant stakeholders identified through partners' suggestions and desk research, involving the mapping of related documents, initiatives, associations, projects, and other relevant sources. This method has been instrumental in building the majority of the stakeholder database and has proven to be highly successful. **Stakeholders reached via this method: 353**
- Direct invitation of stakeholders identified during the case study analyses. **Stakeholders reached via this method: 15**
- Engaging survey responders from T1.2.2 and T1.3 for additional events within SUSTRACK. **Stakeholders reached via this method: 55**
- Notifying and engaging stakeholders who have demonstrated interest through online forms. **Stakeholders reached via this method: 6**
- Coordinating, planning, and promoting stakeholder engagement activities in collaboration with relevant projects and initiatives (detailed in Chapter 5). **Stakeholders reached via this method: Not measured directly, included in direct invitations.**
- Leveraging the networks and channels of project partners, including the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet), through specific calls for interest aimed at attracting potential stakeholders interested in participating in SUSTRACK activities. **Stakeholders reached via this method: Not measured directly.**
- Distributing periodic press releases and newsletters extensively through partners' networks and channels to recruit and keep stakeholders informed and engaged with SUSTRACK initiatives. **Stakeholders reached via this method: Not measured directly.**
- Stakeholders invited directly and indirectly through SUSTRACK website, SUSTRACK social media activities and partners' social media profiles. **Stakeholders reached via this method: Not measured directly, but more than 10000 people reached.**

4.2 SUSTRACK advisory board

The formation of the SUSTRACK Advisory Board (AB) was pivotal, serving as the central hub of our stakeholder network, comprising contributors, multipliers, and adopters. The AB played a crucial role in extending our reach to other stakeholder communities (see Section 2.3). Currently, the AB consists of 7 members who have been actively supporting our engagement efforts by leveraging their networks and disseminating project findings during events. Additionally, their participation in online events has been consistent, further enhancing our project's visibility and impact.

4.3 Overall details of SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement activities

Table 13 lists all the stakeholder engagement activities and their expected timelines, outlines intended outcomes, specifies the stakeholders targeted for each activity, and present the KPIs to measure the efficacy of engagement. The conclusive column is dedicated to verifying the fulfillment of the KPIs.

Table 13 - Sustrack Stakeholder engagement activities

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
Co-creation focus group (T1.2.1), M8	To validate the limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy identified in T1.1	Quadruple Helix (policymakers, businesses, Research and innovation community, NGOs, citizens, etc.)	15 stakeholders	25 stakeholders
T1.2.2: Interviews in English and partner's languages, M8>M13	To complement focus group results	Quadruple Helix (policymakers, businesses, Research and innovation community, NGOs, citizens, etc.)	20 interviews with experts (from at least 10 Member States)	21 interviews conducted, engaging 7 European organisations, 1 international organisation and 6 countries
T1.2.2: Survey, M11	To complement focus group results. The results will be shared during the INSPIRE conference (M12).	European and national policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, NGOs and citizens	Sent to 400 stakeholders in at least 10 Member States, target at least 50 answers (D1.2, M15)	Sent to 396, 55 responses collected, from more than 10 Member States

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
T1.3: Online workshops/meetings, M13>M15	To prioritise identified limits, to produce preliminary guidelines and policy recommendations	European and national policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, NGOs and citizens	At least 15 participants across the EU (D1.3, M18)	20 participants with diverse background
WP2-WP5: Co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working groups, M1>36	To co-create case studies of relevance for the circular bio-economy	4 sectors stakeholders working groups (a) the construction sector; (b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical sector; and (d) the plastic sector	3 co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working groups (> 250 participants across 12 workshops) in the context of the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT conferences	41 participants in the INSPIRE conference
T3.4: Thematic webinars, M23>30	To transfer knowledge (conclusions and recommendations for the four biobased sectors)	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	4 thematic webinars (> 100 participants , 200 views; D3.4, M30)	Not yet started.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
T4.2: Capacity building activities (materials, model tutorials and online webinars), M20>M23	To transfer knowledge and support further applications of the model	Policy makers and authorities, Policy advisors, NGOs/CSOs, Industrial advisors, Industrial associations/clusters, Research and innovation community	At least 4 online webinars (1 for each sector) involving at least 20 stakeholders each, total 80; D4.3, M32)	Not yet started.
T5.1: Policy co-creation workshop, with 4 sectors stakeholders workgroups in the context of the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences through plenary and parallel sessions, M10>M28, M30>M34	To validate derived policy priorities and examples of good policies involving the stakeholders involved in the 4 sectors and the case studies	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40) (D5.3, M32)	47 participants at the INSPIRE conference
T5.1: Prioritisation survey, M33>M34	To provide additional validation to policy priorities and examples of good policies	NGOs/CSOs, Industrial advisors, Industrial associations/clusters, Research and innovation community	Sent to at least 300 stakeholders from at least 10 Member States, target at least 30 answers. (D5.1, D5.2, M18, M34)	Not yet started.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
T5.2: Capacity building for local stakeholders in the context of the DEPLOY conference, M30>M34	To empower local stakeholders through at least one capacity building seminar, to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural).	Policy makers, industry professionals, sustainability, Research and innovation community, system community at national and regional levels in the 6 partner's countries	At least 10 stakeholders per each country (6 countries, total 60 participants ; D5.3, D5.4, M32, M33)	Not yet started.
T5.3: 6 policy roundtable, M30>M34	To have discussions in the partners' respective countries (country partners)	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system community at national and regional levels in the 6 partner's countries	At least 30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total; D5.5, M36)	Not yet started.
T6.2: 3 European conferences (i.e., INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT)*, M1>36	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system community;	At least 250 participants	87 conference participants in the INSPIRE conference

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
		D6.1, D6.2, D6.3		
INSPIRE Conference (Resp: PC+FVA) M12	Conference (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions and facilitate the adoption, replication and exploitation of SUSTRACK results	EU level: Primary targets	> 100 (EU level)	87 participants
	Co-creation workshop (resp. UNIT+ TECNALIA) - WP3 - MS10: To discuss the case studies	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	41 participants
	Policy scenario workshop (T4.1 and T5.1): To verify scenarios developed in T4.1 and contribute to T5.1	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	47 participants

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
DESIGN Conference M20 Conference (Resp: PC+FVA)	Conference (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	EU level: Primary targets	> 50 (EU level)	Not yet started.
	Co-creation workshop (resp BAM+KE) - WP3 - MS10: To discuss the case studies and to define policy priorities and actions across different political levels and policy domains for the sustainable transition, in light of the results of WP3 and WP4; improving the tools and methods of WP2 and WP4	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	
IMPLEMENT Conference M28 (Resp: PC+FVA)	Conference (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions and facilitate the adoption, replication and exploitation of SUSTRACK results	EU level: All target audiences	> 100 (EU level)	Not yet started.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
	<p>Co-creation workshop (resp DBFZ+CIRCE) - T5.3, MS10:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To identify the necessary conditions for the proposed transition pathways; • To prioritise short-, mid- and long-term actions; • To validate policy recommendations (T5.3) 	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	
T6.2: 6 national conferences (i.e., DEPLOY)*, M1>36 (Resp: country partners: Italy-UNIT/FVA; Spain-TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany-BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR; Belgium-UGENT)	Conferences (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by the SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	National level: All target audiences	At least 180 participants	Not yet started.
	6 Policy roundtable discussions in the partners' respective countries (country partners) - T5.3, MS11: To present the revised policy recommendations and guidelines, and ensure that the recommendations and guidelines (both sector- and country specific) are taken up in future policy development	Selected regional and national policy makers (specific) are taken up in future policy development	30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total)	

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
Final Event (Resp: FVA); M36; Final event - MS12	To present the SUSTRACK outcomes	EC and All target audiences	At least 50 participants	Not yet started.

4.3.1 Focus group workshop

The co-creation focus group workshop, demonstrated to be an effective stakeholder engagement event within the broader objective of transitioning towards a circular bio-based economy. Organised in the context of the EU Green Week (Figure 27), the event brought together a diverse set of stakeholders from various EU member countries, targeting SUSTRACK sectors, namely construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles. A total of 25 external participants, including representatives from the research, private, and public sectors, as well as NGOs/CSOs, were engaged in this online workshop held online, on June 9, 2023.

The workshop aimed to validate and enrich understanding around the limits of the linear fossil-based economy, examining barriers and fostering solutions towards the transition to circular bio-based economy. The event was structured to facilitate a rich dialogue among participants. An interactive tool was designed in the MIRO platform through a carefully planned collaborative approach involving all partners (Figure 28). This tool was crucial in ensuring active participation, enabling stakeholders to voice their insights, prioritise barriers, and contribute to the identification of potential solutions in real-time.

Figure 27 - Co-creation focus group workshop

Significantly, the use of tailored MIRO boards stood out for its effectiveness in visualising discussions and feedback. Participants could directly engage with the content, annotating, and voting through live polls on specific barriers and solutions across the discussed sectors.

Stakeholders revised, renamed, validated and suggested additional barriers, enriching those identified by literature review performed by Sustrack partners. Additionally, stakeholders pinpointed specific sectoral challenges, marking a significant step forward in understanding and addressing the multifaceted barriers to a circular bio-based economy.

A screenshot (Figure 28) from the event captures the dynamic discussion between participants, illustrating the collective effort in mapping out the landscape of barriers and solutions. The results of this exercise were a prioritised and enriched list of validated barriers, contributing to a more grounded and comprehensive understanding of the challenges at hand.

Figure 28 - MIRO board interactive exercise during the co-creation focus group workshop

The comprehensive results and methodology have been incorporated into D1.2. Furthermore, the experience of the focus group was consolidated in a conference paper titled "Mapping the Barriers to a Sustainable Transition: Insights from an Extensive Grey Literature Analysis and Focus Group Discussion", currently accepted for presentation (see Section 2.8).

4.3.2 Interviews

In the context of WP1, 57 potential interviewees were identified by SUSTRACK consortium and contacted by BAM or UNITELMA partners.

As part of the task T1.2, **21 experts** from academia, industry, NGOs, and policymakers, representing the Quadruple Helix, were successfully invited to participate in interviews. Detailed information about the interview methodology employed and comprehensive results can be found in D1.2.

4.3.3 Survey

As part of task T1.2, an extensive survey was conducted reaching out **396 stakeholders**. From this pool, a total of **55 responses** were collected. For a comprehensive understanding of the survey methodology employed and a detailed analysis of the results obtained, please refer to D1.2.

4.3.4 Online workshops/meetings with stakeholders

To inform task T1.3, **8 meetings/interviews** were conducted to engage experts owning industry or policymaking experience for the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) and analytic network process (ANP), aiming to gather their valuable feedback.

Since it was difficult to accommodate stakeholders' availability in a limited timeframe, to complement these meetings/interviews prioritising time efficiency while allowing participants to respond at their own convenience, **12 survey responses** were collected. Both meetings/interviews and the survey utilised the same questions.

The outcomes and findings collected from these meetings and the survey, along with a detailed explanation of the methodology employed, have been integrated into D1.3.

4.3.5 INSPIRE conference

The INSPIRE Conference, held online on November 16th, 2023, was a pivotal event organised by the SUSTRACK consortium, targeting a multistakeholder audience across various EU member countries. This conference was designed to foster dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders from the sectors targeted by SUSTRACK, with the ultimate goal of shaping future policies. INSPIRE conference, and more in general the SUSTRACK annual conferences, are key not only for stakeholder engagement, but also for dissemination and communication purposes.

Overview of the Event

The conference successfully attracted 87 unique participants, representing the Quadruple helix stakeholders, including research, industry, public sector, NGOs/CSOs, and relevant project representatives. Consortium partners extended invitations to 360 stakeholders, out of which 132 registered. For details on the distribution across sectors and fields see Figures 29 and 30. The agenda (Figure 31) was thoughtfully structured to maximise engagement and productivity, featuring two plenary sessions, four sector-specific co-creation workshops, and four policy

scenario workshops. The primary objectives were to present and discuss Sustrack comprehensive literature review and findings regarding limits and barriers hindering the transition to circular bio-based economy, delve into the EU monitoring framework along with case studies and developed policy scenarios, with the ultimate goal to pave the way for future policy developments.

Figure 29 - Registered stakeholders by sector

Figure 30 - Registered stakeholders by field

Agenda		
09.00-09.10 Opening speech	Opening speech by Silvia Maltagliati	
09.10-10.10 Plenary session 1	Introduction: An overview of SUSTRACK project outcomes and discoveries <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Barriers, drivers, benefits, gaps towards sustainable transition; ● Existing EU monitoring framework and gaps on indicators and methods used to monitor and evaluate circular bioeconomy; ● Presentation of selected case studies. 	
10.10-12.00 Co-creation workshop (interactive parallel sessions)	Virtual Room 1	Virtual Room 2
	10.10-11.05: Plastics 11.05-12.00: Chemical	10.10-11.05: Construction 11.05-12.00: Textile
12.00-13.00	Lunch break	
13.00-13.10	"EU Bioeconomy Strategy: past and future" - speech by Wim Haentjens	
13.10-13.50 Plenary session 2	Presentation of methodologies, models and results for policy scenarios developed by SUSTRACK.	
13.50-15.50 Scenario workshop (interactive parallel sessions)	Virtual Room 1	Virtual Room 2
	13.50-14.50: Plastics 14.50-15.50: Chemical	13.50-14.50: Construction 14.50-15.50: Textile
15.50-16.00 Closing plenary session	Closing remarks	

Figure 31 - INSPIRE conference agenda

The conference opened with a speech by Silvia Maltagliati, followed by a plenary session that introduced the SUSTRACK project's findings, focusing on the barriers and drivers of sustainable transition and the EU's approach to monitoring circular bioeconomy, including case studies. Interactive, parallel co-creation workshops then took place, with discussions on plastics and chemicals in one virtual room, and construction and textiles in another. After a lunch break, Wim Haentjens discussed the past and future of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. This was followed by a second plenary session presenting methodologies and policy scenario results from SUSTRACK. The afternoon featured scenario workshops continued the morning's discussions in parallel virtual rooms. The conference wrapped up with closing remarks, summarizing the day's insights and discussions.

Interactive Tools Employed

A key to the conference's success was the innovative use of interactive tools, carefully designed to facilitate a high degree of stakeholder engagement.

MIRO Boards: Employed during both the co-creation and policy scenario workshops, tailored MIRO boards offered a versatile platform for collaborative discussion and scenario development, allowing visualisation of complex concepts and results. During the co-creation workshops, participants validated and prioritised specific subtopics, referring to 6 main societal objectives. During the policy scenario workshops, participants validated the policy goals identified by SUSTRACK, and suggested additional ones (Figure 32).

Figure 32 - Screenshot of the MIRO boards used during the INSPIRE conference (left: co-creation workshops; right: policy scenario workshops)

Mentimeter: This tool was utilised during the co-creation workshops to prioritise monitoring indicators, referring to specific subtopics identified with the MIRO board exercise (see above), through real-time feedback and interactive voting (Figure 33).

Figure 33 - Mentimeter interactive tool for prioritisation of indicators

Stakeholder Engagement

The use of interactive tools such as Mentimeter and MIRO boards significantly enhanced the stakeholder engagement process, proving to be effective in reaching the conference's objectives. In particular, the combination of the two carefully designed tools facilitated the immediate visual representation of opinions, enabling the collection focused input from participants.

Results

Co-creation workshops

Co-creation workshops have been instrumental to inform the development of Sustrack monitoring framework (WP2), designed to aid policymakers at different governance levels in the transition to a circular bioeconomy. In the first phase of the project, more than 200 indicators for monitoring and assessing the circular bioeconomy have been identified, encompassing the five

societal objectives outlined by the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. Within this activity, stakeholder engagement in co-creation workshops contributed in prioritising specific subtopics and indicators. These prioritised elements will form the cornerstone of the forthcoming Sustrack bioeconomy dashboard.

As a result of the good number and balanced sectorial/field distribution of participating stakeholders, the outcomes obtained from the sample provide a starting point for further scientific analysis and validation involving a larger number of stakeholders.

From a cross-sectoral perspective, Material use efficiency, Waste prevention reuse and recycling and Sustainable resource use emerged as areas of very high interest overall. Hence, these areas, including underlying indicators, will be promoted (i.e., special attention will be given to these, within the monitoring framework, and, ideally across the case studies).

Chemical sector exhibits a different pattern in terms of relevant topics. Hazardous substances management is the most rated, followed by material use efficiency, innovation and investment, human health and soil quality (Figure 34).

Figure 34 - Summary of prioritized subtopics

In this line, the most relevant indicators in the cross-sectorial subtopics are reported in Figure 35.

Material use efficiency

- Resource use efficiency
- Material circularity
- Cascade factor

Sustainable resource use

- Biobased material replacing non-renewable/fossil resources
- Fossil fuel use intensity
- Resource footprints

Waste prevention, re-use and recycling

- (Municipal) waste recycling and recovery rates
- Existence of procedures/practices for separating waste types from the waste stream to facilitate reuse, recycling or composting
- Share of product is actively being recovered and recycled (or Recycling rate of bio-based products)
- Share of materials used in production process derived from recycling or recovery of biomass waste or by-product

Greenhouse gas emissions

- GHG emissions reductions
- Energy and industrial carbon emissions and removals

Figure 35 - Prioritised indicators in the cross-sectorial subtopics

The selected indicators will be promoted in the monitoring framework as “preliminary key indicators to report on” and special efforts will be dedicated to providing supporting information (including data) for their evaluation and interpretation.

Policy scenario workshops

Policy scenario workshops have been instrumental to validate and expand the two policy portfolio scenarios developed by SUSTRACK in WP4, called “BioTransition” and “BioRevolution”:

- **BioTransition** - Focus on implemented, existing policy goals (focus is on separate collection as preparation for a more circular economy)
- **BioRevolution** - Focus is on more ambitious/revolutionary goals (focus is on advanced goals that transform material flows into circular ones on a higher pace)

These two scenarios, with existing overarching and sector-specific policy goals related to the Circular Bio-based economy transformation, have been validated and 14 additional policy goals were identified by stakeholders (Table 14; Figure 36). Most proposals for additional goals were targeting EU level, reflecting the high importance of the EU policy framework setting goals for a transformation and the need for policy alignment across all EU member states. These additional collected policy goals have been explicitly included in the scenario formulation in D4.1. that are used for the modelling exercise of the circular bioeconomy in the SUSTRACK project.

Table 14 - The additional policy goals identified by stakeholders during the policy scenario workshop

Country	Sector	Policy goal
EU	Construction	<p>1. Oblige/stimulate insulation of all rented houses by 2030/2050</p> <p>2. Establishment of a (mandatory) Digital Product Passport for construction products on European level with - besides others - information regarding repair, reuse, recycling as well as biomass content.</p> <p>3. Buildings renovation quota/targets</p> <p>4. Incentives for the deployment of bio-based materials in construction</p> <p>5. Vacancy management to maintain old buildings and availability of buildings for prolonged usage</p>
Netherlands		<p>6. Guiding goal: by 2030, the Netherlands will use 50% less primary abiotic raw materials (minerals, metals and fossils).</p> <p>7. As many sustainable renewable raw materials are used as possible; products and raw materials are reused; and hardly any waste exists.</p>
EU	Plastic	<p>8. Less use of plastics in agriculture (mulch films, foil tunnels etc.)</p> <p>9. No fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU)</p>
EU	Textile	<p>10. Fortify local/ regional infrastructures to enable sharing of textiles (or other resources)</p> <p>11. Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion (now 30% of fashion in never sold)</p> <p>12. Supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertiliser)</p> <p>13. Increase incentives for bio-based materials in the sector</p> <p>14. Apply carbon tax on all fashion products (and other products) for GHG emissions in full product delivery chain</p>

Figure 36 - The workshop results have been gathered in MIRO Boards, one for each sector (this figure refers to textile sector).

A comprehensive summary of the conference factual findings is available in a form of factsheet (see Section 2.10).

4.4 Lessons learnt and recommendation for the second half of the project

The following section details the discoveries and challenges encountered by the consortium partners in their efforts to engage stakeholders. These valuable lessons serve as crucial guides for structuring future events, guaranteeing increased stakeholder participation, and acquiring high-quality contributions for the project.

Co-creation Focus group workshop

The event format was successful in facilitating the collection of extensive inputs from participants and maintained engagement throughout the workshop. This approach underscored the importance of involving all stakeholders in discussions (including the ones reluctant to speak up) to prevent a polarised dialogue among a few. The live collection of inputs via the MIRO board, however, highlighted the need of having experienced facilitators supporting the process, as well as a sufficient number of them to take notes and report every contribution. The significance of the voting session on the MIRO board in setting priorities was acknowledged. Additionally, a participation rate of 73.5% was reported as high, indicating a successful event format that allowed participants and organisers to stay focused throughout the sessions.

INSPIRE conference

After the INSPIRE Conference, all SUSTRACK partners participated in an internal meeting to collect several key lessons that could inform the planning of future project's events. The main outcomes of this reflection are summarised in this paragraph.

The conference's duration and broad scope were found potentially overwhelming for the stakeholders. To overcome this, future conferences are planned to be split into smaller events, and on different days. In particular, we can imagine a plenary session to present SUSTRACK results (possibly in the context of other big events or conferences, so stakeholders are also already present) and then 4 short workshops, to be organised separately with selected quadruple-helix stakeholders, representative of the different sectors of interest.

A notable challenge was the mismatch between the technical depth of discussions and the general background of participants. To overcome this, we need to ensure that stakeholders have relevant technical expertise, through an improved selection of participants.

The utilisation of interactive tools like Mentimeter and MIRO boards, while effective, highlighted the necessity for pre-event tutorials. To overcome this, we are planning to brief the participants for the interactive parts and sharing materials before the event could maximise participant engagement and minimise overwhelming them.

Sector-specific workshops did not add as much value as expected, providing more cross-sectorial results. Moreover, the division of participants led to reduced interaction and, in some cases, content repetition. To overcome this, we are planning to organise future events separately with selected participants from the targeted sectors.

The technical complexity of some topics emerged as a barrier to broader participation. To overcome this, we are planning to simplify discussions that can accommodate diverse stakeholder backgrounds.

Identifying effective policy goals was challenging for some stakeholders, more interested in the co-creation workshops part. We spotted the need for pre-structured guidance from scientific and policy actors.

Overall, the INSPIRE Conference offered valuable lessons on optimising stakeholder engagement and content delivery to foster meaningful dialogue and collaboration toward sustainable transition goals.

Surveys and Interviews

Surveys are typically effective due to their flexible nature, allowing for the collection of input from relevant stakeholders. Despite what might be considered a low response rate, they have proven effective in achieving specific targets. The survey carried out during T1.2 contacted 396 stakeholders and about 32.07% (127 stakeholders) started it. 55 stakeholders then completed it, yielding a completion rate of approximately 43.31% among those who started, and an overall response rate of 13.89% when considering the total number of stakeholders reached. A shorter and simpler version of the survey could improve the participation and completion rates.

In the case of interviews, the consortium identified and reached out to 57 potential participants. In T1.2 and T1.3, 29 experts accepted invitations to be interviewed, leading to an invitation acceptance rate of around 50%. Taking into consideration the demanding schedules of the targeted experts, the one-to-one approach for contacting them can be considered effective.

5 COLLABORATION WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

SUSTRACK promotes collaborations with relevant EU-funded projects and other initiatives, building on the extensive experience and involvement of partners in several EU-funded projects in the bioeconomy and bio-based domain. For this reason, all partners have access to a number of contacts of projects and initiatives.

FVA also facilitates connection and collaboration with the [European Bioeconomy Network](#) (EuBioNet), being the main promoter of this initiative. EuBioNet is a proactive alliance of more than 150 EU funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support. The main goal is to maximise the efforts, increasing the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, coordination of joint activities and events.

The main objective of this SUSTRACK activity is to cooperate with all the parallel projects dealing with standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring. Nevertheless, SUSTRACK encourages collaboration with the wider community of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem, and specifically the collaboration with EU-funded projects in this domain.

SUSTRACK mapped the concluded and ongoing projects and fostered a collaboration from the beginning of the project. This mapping activity will proceed during the project lifetime, ensuring that the new EU-funded projects will be timely reached and involved.

The collaboration with parallel projects takes place in three different levels of engagement (Figure 37):

- Close collaboration with BIOTRANSFORM (the sister project under HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03);
- Knowledge exchange and alignment with parallel projects (concluded or ongoing) in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring;
- Other types of collaboration or consultation relevant for SUSTRACK activities based on the specific needs identified in the Work Packages.

Figure 37 - Other projects and initiatives collaborating with SUSTRACK

5.1 Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM (organised by SUSTRACK)

During the first 18 months, SUSTRACK organised several activities to liaise with BIOTRANSFORM (parallel project founded under CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03), to increase projects’ impact in addressing EU long term objectives.

The activities organised are summarised in Table 15.

Table 15 - Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM, organised by SUSTRACK

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH BIOTRANSFORM			
Activity and date	Objectives	Target participants (impact)	KPI foreseen
1 st Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshop, 14 February 2023	See Section 5.2	See Section 5.2	See Section 5.2
Addition of BIOTRANSFORM as Sister Project section on SUSTRACK website	See Section 5.2	See Section 5.2	See Section 5.2
Online “cooperation launching event”, 9 March 2023	<p>To identify similarities and differences and possible synergies among projects;</p> <p>To set up a roadmap for cooperation;</p> <p>To creation of a Permanent Liaison Round (PLRT) Table to ensure proactive collaboration among the two projects;</p> <p>To operationalize the collaboration among the two sister projects.</p>	1 EC representative (policy officer), 3 projects’ coordinators/manager, 4 communication managers and 6 WP leaders (14 in total).	<p>>6 participants</p> <p>PLRT composed by at least 2 representatives per project</p>

<p>First Thematic Discussion Meeting, 20 April 2023</p>	<p>To share and discuss the results of the research that both projects are performing on limits/gaps of linear fossil-based economy;</p> <p>To identify similarities, differences and possible synergies among the results, to avoid overlap and promote mutual learning;</p> <p>To discuss and operationalise the next collaboration opportunities and joint activities based on projects' work plan.</p>	<p>3 representatives of PLRT, 11 WP/task leaders (14 in total)</p>	<p>At least 4 meetings during SUSTRACK</p>
<p>SUSTRACK INSPIRE Conference, 16 November 2023</p>	<p>To present SUSTRACK comprehensive literature review and main findings that serve as the backbone for our discussions.</p> <p>To dive deep into the existing EU monitoring framework.</p> <p>To present and discuss case studies and preliminary findings.</p> <p>To present and discuss developed policy scenarios.</p>	<p>9 representatives of BIOTRANSFORM project</p>	<p>N.A.</p>

5.1.1 Online “Cooperation Launching Event” (9 March 2023)

In the “Cooperation Launching Event” (Figure 38), the projects participating received beforehand a PPT template and provided an overview of the main objectives, expected outcomes, sectors of interest, methodologies and tools, Work Packages overview of objectives and activities, in order to identify similarities and differences and possible synergies among projects, kick-off the collaboration and define the strategy.

During the second part of the workshop, the participants interacted with the collaborative online tool MIRO board to plan future joint activities.

The event led to a fruitful discussion among the project’s representatives, who agreed a joint action plan. Specifically, the projects agreed to organise periodic thematic discussions in key milestones of the projects, based on their work plan, common topics of interest and specific activities targeting similar stakeholders. Specifically, the following topics have been identified as common and relevant:

- limits/gaps/barriers of the linear economy;
- methodologies and tools to assess the sustainability;
- stakeholder engagement activities;
- reciprocal harmonisation and consolidation of policy recommendations.

In particular, the projects agreed to organise a first thematic discussion in April 2023 (see Section 5.1.2), focusing on limits/gaps/barriers of the linear economy.

Moreover, SUSTRACK and BIOTRANSFORM agreed to communicate timely and mutually the relevant events and invite each other to participate in these events with the aim of inspiring and cross-fertilising each other.

Finally, the Permanent Liaison Round Table (PLRT) was established, composed by projects' representatives of coordination and communication (2 people per project).

FVA sent the recording, presentations and minutes for partners consultation.

Figure 38 - Screenshots from the online “Cooperation Launching Event”

5.1.2 First Thematic Discussion Meeting (20 April 2023)

In the “First Thematic Discussion Meeting” (Figure 39), the projects participating prepared a PPT presentation to share the results of the research performed on limits/gaps/barriers of linear economy and the main points/questions to discuss.

The event led to a fruitful discussion among the project’s, enriched by several questions, comments and suggestions to improve each other’s research. It was agreed that SUSTRACK will invite BIOTRANSFORM in the incoming (9 June 2023, 10-13 CEST) Focus Group (T1.2.1) to discuss and validate with Quadruple helix stakeholders limits/gaps/barriers of linear fossil-based economy, and at the INSPIRE conference (November 2023), to share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions, to discuss the case studies and to verify policy scenarios.

Finally, SUSTRACK and BIOTRANSFORM agreed to align on next foreseen collaborations and thematic discussions via email. The next meeting is foreseen in May 2024. A preliminary exchange via email is taking place to identify common topics of interest to make the workshop more focused.

Figure 39 - Screenshots from the “1st Thematic Discussion Meeting”

5.2 Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” (organised by Sustrack)

To maximise the impact of project outcomes by promoting mutual learning and the sharing of common challenges, and boosting the valorisation of existing knowledge, the project promotes collaboration with the most relevant parallel projects in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring. This collaboration takes place in two different forms:

- with concluded projects, Sustrack project facilitates the knowledge transfer of exploitable assets to maximise the usage of the outcomes stemming from these projects;
- with ongoing parallel projects, Sustrack project promotes mutual learning, sharing of common challenges, and the valorisation of existing knowledge within parallel projects and initiatives fostering the transition from fossil-based, carbon-intensive systems to circular, bio-based systems.

The list of projects identified as relevant for collaboration are presented in Table 16.

Table 16 - Projects identified for collaboration

PROJECTS IDENTIFIED FOR COLLABORATION		
Projects	Funding	Type of collaboration established
STAR-ProBio	BB-01-2016	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
STAR4BBI	BBI 2015	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
BIOMONITOR	BB-02-2017	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website

BIOTRANSFORM	CIRCBIO-01-03	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
STAR4BBS	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
HARMONITOR	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
CALIMERO	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-06	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
ALIGNED	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-06	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
BIORECER	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-05	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
3-CO	2022-GOV-01-04	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
CEE2ACT	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-10	“Sister project” section on website
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative	https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/	“Sister project” section on website

These objectives will be implemented through the following activities organised by SUSTRACK (Table 17).

Table 17 - Clustering activities with projects in “Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”, organised by SUSTRACK

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER PARALLEL PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES IN “STANDARDISATION, CERTIFICATION, LABELLING AND MONITORING”			
Activity and date	Objectives	Target participants (impact)	KPI foreseen

<p>1st Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshop, 14 February 2023</p>	<p>To share methodologies, lessons learnt and findings.</p>	<p>Representatives of the following projects (12 projects, 40 people in total): STAR-ProBio STAR4BBI BIOMONITOR SUSTRACK BIOTRANSFORM STAR4BBS SUSTCERT4BIOBASE D HARMONITOR CALIMERO ALIGNED BIORECER 3-CO</p>	<p>At least 30 participants in total</p>
<p>Sister Project section on SUSTRACK website</p>	<p>To leverage on each other's website for visibility exchange</p>	<p>12 projects</p>	<p>NA</p>
<p>2nd Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshops</p>	<p>To provide insights to refine the SUSTRACK results and recommendations, and will facilitate the exploitation of the project outcomes.</p>	<p>Other relevant projects and initiatives</p>	<p>At least 30 participants in total</p>

5.2.1 1st Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop (14 February 2023)

In preparation of the SUSTRACK kick-off, before SUSTRACK project launch, in the context of the workshop “Projects2Projects” organised by EuBioNet as satellite event of the “High Level Bioeconomy Conference” (6, 7 October 2022, Brussels), some SUSTRACK partners supported the EuBioNet in facilitating the discussion among projects involved in “Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”. The main outcome of this workshop was the establishment of a thematic working group on these topics, to pave the way to further activities under SUSTRACK project.

On 14 February 2023, SUSTRACK organised online the first Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MML) Workshop of the working group in “Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” (Figure 40), in collaboration with EuBioNet. This workshop has been an important stepping stone for the future collaborations among projects with similar focus and facilitated the uptake of exploitable assets stemming from concluded projects by the recently started projects under

Horizon Europe. Many opportunities for collaborations have been identified and will serve as guidance for defining collaboration strategies among projects, namely:

- establish advisory boards with representatives of all projects;
- promote collaboration among communication managers;
- align stakeholder engagement activities;
- encourage continuous mutual learning among projects;
- jointly identify exploitation pathways.

In addition, projects agreed on discussing further common challenges and activities, such as:

- identification of criteria for value chains prioritisation;
- monitoring frameworks at EU/country/region/city/value-chain/product levels.

Finally, all projects participating at the MML agreed to become SUSTRACK “Sister Projects”, in order to leverage on each other’s website for visibility exchange (see Section 5.2.2).

FVA sent the recording, presentations and minutes for EC and partners consultation.

Figure 40 - Screenshots from the 1st MML workshop

5.2.2 “Sister projects” section on SUSTRACK website

Stemming from the 1st MML workshop, SUSTRACK created a dedicated [“Sister Projects” section](#) on its website, where other projects are briefly presented and linked, in order to leverage on each other’s website for visibility exchange. Sister Projects are included in this section (Figure 41), and SUSTRACK is included in theirs.

Figure 41 - “Sister project” section on SUSTRACK website

5.3 Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” in which SUSTRACK representatives participated

SUSTRACK not only organised activities to cluster with other parallel projects and initiatives, but also participated with representatives in several activities organised by those projects, to strengthen the liaisons (Figure 42). A summary of all these activities is listed in the Table 18.

Table 18 - Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”, in which SUSTRACK participated

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER PARALLEL PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES IN “STANDARDISATION, CERTIFICATION, LABELLING AND MONITORING” IN WHICH SUSTRACK PARTICIPATED	
Activity and date	Objectives
ZP-01-07 Cluster Joint Advisory Board kick-off meeting (SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS projects), 24 February 2023	<p>The aim of the meeting was to introduce SUSTRACK and the three projects and shortly present on the 2 topics of interest currently to get our input and feedback: Development of a joint monitoring system and Selection of biobased value chains.</p> <p>In preparation for this meeting, we also filled an excel file (Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)) methodology to rank/prioritize the biobased value chains. In order to do so, different criteria and sub-criteria have been defined, and we assessed the importance of each of these criteria and sub-criteria for a biobased value chain.</p>

<p>BioReCer workshop, 13 March 2023</p>	<p>Workshop to present BioReCer, its main objectives and expected results, and to collect feedback and engage stakeholders in the project.</p>
<p>Registration in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network Of Interest (NOI), 16 March 2023</p>	<p>SUSTRACK registered as part of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest</p>
<p>Interview with a 18-months research project (Tender, NORION Consult) aimed to identify and develop potential improvements on the monitoring of the circular economy across the EU, 14 April 2023</p>	<p>Interview on technical aspects of how to measure/assess the impacts of a circular bio-based economy, with Ms. Lea Kress, Norion Danimark Environmental Consultant</p>
<p>1st SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest meeting, 16 June 2023</p>	<p>The main objective of this meeting was to meet the members of the network of interest for the first time and update the members about the progress of the project. Also, a brief introduction to the Green Claim Regulation and the role of voluntary certification schemes was presented.</p>
<p>3-CO and BioReCer workshop - Joint activities of our Horizon EU projects, 13 October 2023</p>	<p>Collecting ideas for online and offline activities and physical material that could be jointly prepared among projects.</p>
<p>BioReCer Annual Stakeholder Meeting, 13 November 2023</p>	<p>Workshop to present BioReCer, and discuss about Circular economy indicators and EU Green Claim Directive.</p>
<p>2nd SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest meeting, 4 December 2023</p>	<p>The main objectives of this meeting were to present the research updates from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, also regarding the Joint Monitoring System they are developing. A brief overview about how the certification process works was also done.</p>

Figure 42 - Screenshots from some clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” in which Sustrack participated

5.4 Clustering activities with other projects and initiatives in bioeconomy

In parallel with the above-mentioned focused collaborations and activities, Sustrack encourages collaboration with the wider community of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem, and specifically the collaboration with EU-funded projects in this domain, but also with relevant initiatives. These collaborations are facilitated also by [EuBioNet](#), in which [Sustrack is partner](#) since the beginning of the project.

5.4.1 Clustering activities with ECOSYSTEEX initiative

In February 2023, Sustrack joined the [ECOSYSTEEX initiative](#), as part of the “founding” members. With 28 EU-funded member projects focusing on textile sustainability, ECOSYSTEEX, the European Community of Practice for a Sustainable Textile Ecosystem, has been formally launched in early 2023, with a mission to accelerate collaboration in the textile sustainability and circularity field (Figure 43).

As a joint initiative of the European Commission’s Research Executive Agency (REA), the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) and the Circular-Biobased Europe Joint Undertaking, and facilitated by the Textile ETP, this new network of textile circularity projects aims to create a long-term community of practice, ensuring collaboration across project consortia and lasting beyond the individual projects’ durations.

Figure 43 - ECOSYSTEMX initiative

In this context, SUSTRACK joined several ECOSYSTEMX Working Groups (HG1 - Research and Innovation Gaps and Needs; HG2 - Joint dissemination, which meet periodically, TG1 - Environmental Assessment & Product Environmental Footprint; TG3 - Ecodesign for Safe and Sustainable Materials, Products & Processes) and participated in several activities organised by ECOSYSTEMX, with different objectives:

- Dissemination and communication purposes (specifically described in Chapter 3);
- Being updated about activities and results by the other members;
- Establish synergies among projects involved in ECOSYSTEMX.

A summary of the activities (Figure 44) is reported in Table 19.

Table 19 - Summary of the activities with ECOSYSTEMX (not including the dissemination and communication activities)

ACTIVITIES WITH ECOSYSTEMX (NOT INCLUDING DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES)		
Activity and date	Objectives	Target participants (impact)
ECOSYSTEMX First Steering Committee Meeting , 21 March 2023	Establishing synergies among projects involved in the platform via creating working groups	~20 participants Projects participated: CISUTAC, waste2biocomp, my.fi, TRICK, HW, effective, ALIGNED, white cycle, SUSTRACK, t-rex, tExtended, new cotton project,

		Glaukos, GRETE, SCIRT, CIRPASS, IRISS
HG2 - Joint Dissemination, 26 April 2023	<p>Organise the communication and dissemination activities of ECOSYSTEMEX</p> <p>Amplify the results of the ECOSYSTEMEX projects</p> <p>Promote the activities and results of ECOSYSTEMEX as a whole, and the other ECOSYSTEMEX Working Groups (when possible due to IPR)</p> <p>Organise joined dissemination events</p> <p>Increase membership of ECOSYSTEMEX Internally share best practices among projects</p>	12 participants
HG1 - Research and Innovation Gaps and Needs, 28 April 2023	<p>Proposal and discussion of research and innovation gaps and needs for sustainable textile</p>	<p>~20 participants</p> <p>Projects participated: Glaukos, tExtended, CISUTAC, CIRPASS, TRICK, IRISS, White cycle, Scirt, ALIGNED, SUSTRACK, Framework for Circular Textiles</p>
HG2 - Joint Dissemination, 6 October 2023	<p>Organise the communication and dissemination activities of ECOSYSTEMEX</p> <p>Amplify the results of the ECOSYSTEMEX projects</p> <p>Promote the activities and results of ECOSYSTEMEX as a whole, and the other ECOSYSTEMEX Working Groups (when possible due to IPR)</p> <p>Increase membership of ECOSYSTEMEX Internally share best practices among projects</p> <p>Presentation and feedbacks to the ECOSYSTEMEX dissemination and communication strategy</p>	12 participants
ECOSYSTEMEX General Assembly	<p>Overview of ECOSYSTEMEX in numbers and updates on ECOSYSTEMEX Working Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HG1 - Research and Innovation Gaps and Needs: The first publication; 	70 participants

<p>Meeting, 8 November 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TG1 - Environmental Assessment and PEF: Developments and what's next; • TG2 - Assessment of Different Recycling Technologies and EoL Options: Developments and what's next; • TG3 - SSbD and ESPR: Developments and what's next; • TG4 - Renewable Materials and Standards: Developments and what's next; • HG2 - Joint dissemination: Opportunities to disseminate project results at ECOSYSTEK Conference 	
<p>HG2 - Joint Dissemination, 30 November 2023</p>	<p>Collect feedbacks from the ECOSYSTEK Conference</p> <p>Present the upcoming ECOSYSTEK Insights Series in 2024, to offer opportunity for dissemination to ECOSYSTEK members</p> <p>Present the 2024 ECOSYSTEK Conference</p> <p>Promote ECOSYSTEK projects members news and event (Sustrack survey was promoted during this meeting)</p>	<p>9 participants</p>
<p>ECOSYSTEK Technical Working Group TG 1 - Environmental Assessment & Product Environmental Footprint</p> <p>Meeting dates: 25 April 2023 13 July 2023 31 August 2023 13 October 2023</p>	<p>Represent Sustrack project in the working group meetings, present information about our project and our expertise related to LCA and circularity assessment, participate in discussions concerning methodologies and tools used in sustainability assessment and LCA methods used</p>	<p>ECOSYSTEK members (about 20 people) with expertise on topic of environmental assessment</p>
<p>ECOSYSTEK Technical Working Group TG 3 - Ecodesign for Safe and Sustainable Materials,</p>	<p>Represent Sustrack project in the working group meetings, present information about our project on the relevant topics, discussion on potential collaboration with other EU projects as members of this group</p>	<p>ECOSYSTEK members (about 20 people) with expertise on ecodesign and safe and sustainable by design framework</p>

<p>Products & Processes</p> <p>Meeting dates: 26 April 2023 24 May 2023 22 June 2023 30 August 2023 4 October 2023 22 November 2023</p>	
--	--

Figure 44 - Screenshots from different activities with ECOSYSTEMX

5.5 Lessons learnt and next steps

As a result of Sustrack commitment in promoting the collaboration with other projects and initiatives, the major results of this task have been:

- Knowledge exchange;
- Participation to each other’s events and activities;
- Cross-validation of results;
- Alignment of activities
- Dissemination activities leveraging each other’s channels and networks (see Chapter 3).

Some lessons learnt and recommendations can be outlined as well:

- the closest parallel projects are not necessarily the most similar in terms of objectives, expected results and outcomes. There may be other projects under different calls that could be more similar, therefore an accurate and continuous monitoring activity is needed.
- projects have different objective and timeframes, therefore it might not be possible to fully align the work, despite the willingness;
- many projects are doing similar activities with the same stakeholders, thus there is a risk of competition and duplication: the alignment and the possibility to organise joint events can be a solution (whenever possible);
- it is important to facilitate a broader dialogue among all projects, not just the parallel ones or the closest ones.
- the aggregation of results in joint factsheets is highly recommended to increase the impact and adoption by the intended target audiences (e.g., policy makers).

6 NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSION

This deliverable represents the first report on the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities and it resumes tools, materials, social media campaigns and activities performed to support SUSTRACK project promotion.

The strategies and key messages to be conveyed through the different SUSTRACK channels will be constantly updated, according to the various phases of the project.

FVA, as dissemination and communication leader, and PEDAL, as stakeholder engagement leader, will be proactive and motivate all partners to contribute and share content and information about SUSTRACK project among their networks and keep tracking of the activities through the monitoring tools.

The second version of this deliverable, covering from M18 to M36 will be delivered on M36.

Project Consortium

